

Self-concept and its relationship to the academic field among early childhood education students

Afaf Mamdouh Mohamed Barakat^{*1,2}, Ahlam A. Gabr³, Alaa Mustafa⁴, Rasmeya Mohamed Metwalli^{3,5}

1Department of Education, college of Arts and Science Rafha, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia.

2 Department of Basic Science, college of Education Early Childhood, Fayoum University, Egypt.

3Fayoum university, college of early childhood education, Department of Psychological Sciences

4Department of Mathematics, College of science, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia.

5Northern Border University, college of Arts and Science Turaif, Department of Education, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract

The study aimed to get to know self-concept among female students of the Faculty of Early Childhood Education, Fayoum University, and female students of the Early Childhood Education Program, Northern Border University, and its relationship to the academic field, in addition to determining the role of the variables of specialization, college, and nationality on self-concept. To achieve this, the study was conducted on a sample of (120) female students, divided into 30 female students from the Early Childhood Education Program at Northern Border University, 30 female students from the Early Childhood Special Education Program, 30 female students from the Early Childhood Program in English, and 30 female students from the Nursery Teachers Program.

The results of the study showed that the degree of self-concept was high in all areas and the total degree, while the differences were not statistically significant in the total degree of self-concept according to the variables of nationality, specialization, and college. The study recommended several recommendations, the most important of which is paying attention to extracurricular activities because of their positive role in refining the personality of female students and developing their self-concept. Strengthening the self-concept of early childhood students through activities related to the social aspect and enhancing the positive aspects of the self-concept, as this has an impact on the self-concept of children who will learn at the hands of these teachers.

Keywords— (Self-concept- Academic field- Early childhood)

Introduction

The concept of self in contemporary psychology is an effective system of concepts, values, goals, and ideals that determine the way an individual behaves (Abu Zaid, 2017). If the self is formed, it maintains its organization and resists modification, change, and division, which greatly helps in predicting the behavior of individuals in different situations. Progress in behavior is due to the stability of the self, the stability of its goals and methods, and this does not mean that it never changes. The individual lives in a society that is the mirror in which he sees himself, and for this reason the individual changes himself as long as his behavior contradicts the society in which he lives, and whenever people's point of view changes towards him

(2020, Quilter)

Contemporary researchers in the field of psychology and counseling have been interested in studying the concept of the self and identifying its dimensions, levels, and functions, and its impact on the individual's behavior. Among these scholars are Allport, Adler, Kooley Parice Meed, Dewey, and others. However, the most interested in the concept of the self was the scientist Rogers, who made the concept the basis for his theory of psychotherapy and counseling. This theory was known as "the theory of the self or the theory centered around the client

(2021, Yang)

The study of the concept of self and its esteem is one of the topics that still occupies the first place in psychological research. The individual lives in circumstances filled with variables that have a direct impact on him, increasing the rates of stress and psychological and physical illness, preventing the healthy individual from adapting, and thus having a fundamental impact on his personality, which leads to a malfunction in one of the important systems in the personality, perhaps one of which is the concept of self

(2013, Rasmyah)

The concept of self is formed since childhood through the different stages of growth in light of certain determinants through which the individual gradually acquires his idea of himself and describes himself. It is the product of patterns of social upbringing and social interaction, positions, experiences, methods of reward and punishment, parental trends and their generalizations, and cognitive, social and emotional experiences that the individual goes through, such as; experiences of success and failure, social role, in addition to the economic and social status, and other matters related to frustration and conflict

(Barakat, AMMAR, Gabr, AAA, & Hassan, HH F. (2020)) & (2022, Metwalli)

The concept of self consists of a unified set of aspects that can be analyzed by means of measurement procedures. It has a hierarchical environment based on the individual's broad private Sub-concepts. (2017, Dockery) experiences, which are included over time in school, home, and society about his physical, emotional, social, and academic self are formed, which come together and combine to form the general concept of the self. The concept of self is the overall image and awareness that the individual has of himself, his unique characteristics, and his behavior related to the physical, social, emotional, and mental aspects of the self

(2018, Elizabeth)

It is worth noting that various studies have shown that the concept of self is closely linked to the ,Enam) motivation to learn, and that the most important ideas are those that the learner has about himself which are the result of the experiences, attitudes and experiences of the classroom, school and , (2021 university, and that students with low academic achievement tend to have weak academic self-concepts and negative feelings about the self, while students with higher achievement tend to have more positive concepts about themselves and their academic abilities

(Gearheart, 2016) & (2009, Elliott)

Hence, the importance of studying the concept of self among university students appears, as it indicates to that phase the university phase a task to qualify youth to bear for (Lerner, 2013) & (Jensen, that (2016 responsibility to win knowledge the truth while related with supplies the era from sciences and the as well as that its period numbers individual and his rehabilitation to , (2021, Yang) technology confront problems the society, and then the job on increase production, as it is considered phase the university phase unique in qualification individual scientifically

confirms this by considering the stage education university field fertile and abundant (Jensen, 2013)

source to support communities modernity with cadres eligible in various areas life and on amount from care and interest with these youth determine continuity investment their energies, and their capabilities, in activities and works useful they acquire from during it many from information and experiences that contribute in facing many from problems life daily

(Quilter, 2015)

Importance of the study

In light of the above, the importance of conducting this study appears and can be summarized as follows

- 1- The current study is considered one of the recent studies in the Northern Borders and Fayoum that is concerned with studying the concept of self among early childhood students
- 2- The results of the current study are expected to provide a clear picture of the concept of self among female students majoring in early childhood in Fayoum and the Northern Borders. Thus providing university officials with feedback on strengths and working to enhance them
- 3- It is expected through the results of the study to identify the role of the variables of nationality, college, and specialization on the self-concept of early childhood students at Fayoum University and the Northern Borders
- 4- It is expected that the theoretical framework of the study and its results will benefit researchers in conducting other similar studies in this field

The study problem and its questions

The problem of the current research stems from the fact that the positive and negative aspects of the self-concept greatly affect the personal and social adaptation of the individual. They affect the various aspects of the personality: physical, social, emotional and mental. Disturbance of this concept leads to disturbance of the individual's behavior. This is reflected in his work with children in the future (Lo, Ch . 2008)

confirms that positive self-concept affects the learning process. March confirms that positive self-concept in children under the age of ten leads to high academic achievement and attainment because this period of their lives is crucial in forming a positive self-concept, especially in educational institutions. This concept is certainly instilled in children by their teachers

If an individual has a negative self-concept, his or her way of speaking and the way he or she expresses his or her feelings toward himself or toward others is described as lacking self-respect and social intelligence. Hence, the problem of the study appeared to the researcher, and it can be summarized by answering the following questions

1. What is the degree of self-concept among early childhood students at Northern Border University and Fayoum University?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ of early childhood students due to the nationality variable?
3. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ of early childhood students? Back to the specialization variable?
4. Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ of early childhood students due to the college variable?

Study objectives :The study aimed to achieve the following objectives

- 1- Identifying the level of self-concept among early childhood students at Fayoum University and Northern Border University
- 2- Identifying the role of each of the variables (nationality, specialization college) on the self-concept of early childhood students

Fields of study

- 1- **Spatial scope :** Faculty of Early Childhood Education in Fayoum and Early Childhood Education Program at Northern Border University
- 2- **Human field :** Students of early childhood programs at Fayoum University and Northern Border University
- 3- **Time frame :** The study was conducted in the first semester of 2024

Study terms

The researcher committed to defining and interpreting the terms as defined by Abu Nahia, as follows

Academic field : refers to the individual’s concept and awareness of his academic abilities in terms of his behavior, his ability to memorize, explain it well to his colleagues, his feeling of satisfaction with his work, and his degree of perseverance and academic achievement

Physical domain: refers to the individual’s concept and awareness of his physical appearance – which includes physical abilities and characteristics that have social significance – such as general appearance, facial image, and the extent to which he feels satisfied and content with his physical qualities and abilities

Social domain: refers to the individual’s concept and awareness of his relationships with others and his position among them, whether they are his colleagues, friends in society, or family. It refers to the extent to which others love him , his ability to make friends, and the extent to which he feels respected and accepted by others

Self-confidence domain: refers to the individual’s concept and awareness of the aspects of self-confidence, emotional balance, and lack of fear. It refers to the extent to which the individual feels fear, anxiety, and happiness, and is described as moody, or nervous, or as being annoyed by others or different from them

The concept of the total self

It is the individual's concept and awareness of the various elements that make up the personality or his internal and external being

As for the operational definition: it is the degree that the respondent obtains on the Abu Nahia scale for self-concept

Study sample

The study was conducted on a sample of (120) female undergraduate students in the scientific and literary colleges at the Northern Borders University and Fayoum . The sample represents approximately of the total community of the Northern Borders and 50% of the total community of Fayoum (% 100)

1. Nationality

Table (1)

Description of the study sample according to the nationality variable

(%) Percentage	Nationality
25	1) Saudi Arabia
75	Egypt
%100	the total

2. College

Table (2)

Description of the study sample according to the college variable

(%) Percentage	Repetition	College
25	30	breeding
75	90	Science and literature

3. : Specialization

Table (3)

Description of the study sample according to the specialization variable

(%) Percentage	Specialization
30.2	Early Childhood Year
19.6	Special education
25.1	early childhood in english
25.1	Nursery teachers

4

Study tool

In this study, the researcher used the Abu Nahia scale to measure the self-concept . The scale consists of paragraphs distributed over (4) domains, as in Table (4) (80)

Table (4)

Scale domains and number of items for each domain

Number of paragraphs	Areas
20	Academic field
20	physical field
20	Social field
20	Self-confidence field
80	Total complex

Scientific parameters of the tool

Tool validity

The self-reliability of the scale was used by the square root of reliability, which is 0.953, which is a high level of reliability that meets the purposes of the study

Tool stability

In order to determine the stability of the tool, Cronbach's alpha equation was used for a sample of female students , (25) students in Fayoum , and (25) students in the northern border. This sample was (50) taken from university students, and the self-concept scale was applied to them with the aim of identifying the stability of the tool, and Table (5) shows this, and they were not included in the study sample

Table (5)

Stability of the study tool using Cronbach's alpha equation (n = 50)

stability	Areas
0.9	Academic field
0.87	physical field
0.88	Social field
0.86	Self-confidence field
0.91	Total stability

It is clear from Table (5) that the stability coefficients of the tool on the tool domains ranged between (0.86-0.9 5) and on the tool as a whole to (0.91), and all of these are high stability coefficients that meet the purposes of the study

Study procedures

The following are the most important steps followed by the researcher in conducting the study

1. Preparing Abu Nahia scale to measure self-concept
2. Defining the study community, which included undergraduate students majoring in early childhood in the Northern Borders and Fayoum
3. Determine the study sample
4. The reliability of the scale was carried out by taking a sample from the original community and conducting the Cronbach's alpha equation in order to determine the reliability of the scale
5. The researcher distributed the questionnaires to all sample members
6. The data were statistically processed using SPSS.
7. Presentation, analysis, discussion, conclusions and recommendations

Study design

First: Independent Variables :

1. Nationality has two levels . Egypt , Saudi Arabia
2. The college has two levels: Education, Science and Arts
3. The specialization has four levels: general childhood, special education, childhood in English, and nursery teachers

Second: Dependent Variables :

The response includes the domains of the self-concept scale and the total score of the scale

Statistical treatments

was used using the SPSS In order to process the data, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences following statistical processors

1. .Cronbach's alpha formula to find the reliability coefficient
2. - . test
3. One . Way ANOVA

Presentation and discussion of results

First: Results related to the first question

What is the degree of self-concept among early childhood students? At the Northern Border University and Fayoum students

To answer the question, I used arithmetic means and percentages for each domain and for the total .score of self-concept, and the results of the table show that

Table (6)

Arithmetic means and percentages of the concept of early childhood students Northern Borders

Self-concept level	Percentage (%)s	Average response	Areas
high	97.5	39	Academic field
high	95	38	physical field
high	97.5	39	Social field
high	95	38	Self-confidence field
high	96.25	154	Total score

Arithmetic means and percentages of the concept of early childhood students In Fayoum			
high	97.5	39	Academic field
high	85	34	physical field
high	92.5	37	Social field
high	80	32	Self-confidence field
high	88.75	142	Total score

It is clear from the table that the percentage of response to the self-concept domains (academic, physical, social, self-confidence) and the total score of self-concept among female students Early childhood was all expressing a high level of self-concept among the female students of the two universities , and the researcher believes that the reason for this may be due to the interest in academic guidance, direction and counseling, and the educational and social experiences available to the female students of the two colleges

Second: Results related to the second question

in the self-concept $0.05 = \alpha$ Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level of early childhood students? Back to the nationality variable and the results of Independent t-test for two independent groups, To answer this question, use the .the table show that

Table (7)

Results of the (t) test for the significance of differences in self-concept according to the nationality variable

Statistical significance level	Calculated value of (t)	Saudi Arabia		Egypt		Areas
		deviation	Average	deviation	Average	
*0.009	37.2	67.5	21.05	6.04	19.95	Academic field
*0.003	21.3	4.78	20.70	5.41	19.59	physical field
*0.000	42.4	5.76	23.97	6.003	22.23	Social field
0.07	91.1	5.16	21.90	5.48	21.20	Self-confidence field
*0.000	84.1	14.35	87.63	16.63	82.97	Total score

It is clear from Table (10) that the value of (t) calculated on the self-confidence domain was equal to (1.9 and this value is smaller than the tabular value (1.96), meaning that there are no significant differences (1 in the self-concept on this domain due to the nationality variable , while $0.05 = \alpha$ at the significance level the values of (t) calculated on the other domains and the total score were greater than the value of (t) table on $0.05 = \alpha$ meaning that there are statistically significant differences at the significance level ,(1.96) these domains and the total score between Egypt and Saudi Arabia in favor of Saudi Arabia

Third: Results related to the third question

in the self-concept of $0.05 = \alpha$ Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level early childhood students due to the college variable and the results of Independent t-test for two independent groups, To answer this question, use the .the table show that

Table (8)

Results of the (t) test for the significance of differences in self-concept according to the college variable

Statistical significance level	Calculated value of (t)	Science and literature		breeding		Areas
		deviation	Average	deviation	Average	
0.52	0.63	5.83	20.60	5.88	20.31	Academic field
0.50	0.66	5.40	20.05	4.56	20.31	physical field
0.40	0.82	6.01	22.96	5.82	23.34	Social field
0.97	0.02	5.41	21.55	5.07	21.54	Self-confidence field
0.77	0.28	16.53	85.18	13.98	85.52	Total score

It is clear from the table that the calculated (t) values for all fields and the total score for the concept are smaller than the tabular value (1.96), meaning that there are no statistically significant differences at the in the concept of self among early childhood students between students of the $0.05 = \alpha$ significance level College of Education and the College of Arts and Sciences. The researcher believes that the reason for the lack of differences between them may be due to the similarity of educational and methodological conditions in the two colleges for female students, regardless of the college to which they belong

Fourth: Results related to the fourth question

Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ in the self-concept of early childhood students? Is it due to the specialization variable ? To answer this question, I used arithmetic means and one-way ANOVA .

Table (9)

Arithmetic means of self-concept among the study sample members according to the variable

Specialization

Nursery teachers	Childhood English	Special education	Childhood of the year	Areas
2 21.3	2 19.6	6 20.3	5 20.7	Academic field
20.30	1 20.0	19.98	6 20.3	physical field
6 24.0	3 23.3	7 22.5	1 22.3	Social field
8 21.5	9 21.4	5 21.4	9 21.7	Self-confidence field
8 87.2	7 84.4	7 84.3	2 85.2	Total score

Table (10)

Results of one-way analysis of variance for the significance of differences in self-concept according to the specialization variable

Statistical significance	Calculated value of (F)	Average deviation	sum of squares of deviation	Source of variance	Areas
--------------------------	-------------------------	-------------------	-----------------------------	--------------------	-------

*0.03	2.82	96.06 33.96	288.18 26153.30 26441.48	Between groups Within groups the total	Academic field
0.85	0.26	7.03 26.43	21.10 20352.10 20373.20	Between groups Within groups the total	physical field
*0.02	3.21	112.78 35.08	338.34 27012.58 27350.92	Between groups Within groups the total	Social field
0.97	0.07	2.22 28.56	6.63 21996.64 22003.32	Between groups Within groups the total	Self-confidence field
0.21	1.49	368.15 246.20	1104.46 189577.99 190682.46	Between groups Within groups the total	Total score

It is clear from the previous table that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance in the self-concept of early childhood students in two areas (physical, and self-confidence), $0.05 = \alpha$ level and the total score is due to the specialization variable, while the differences were statistically significant in the two areas (academic, and social) according to the specialization variable

Recommendations

In light of the study objectives and results, the researcher recommends the following

- 1- university administration's interest in extracurricular activities in order to develop students' personalities and self-concept
- 2- The necessity of paying attention to the self-concept of female students at Fayoum University, as the results showed that Saudi Arabia is superior in self-concept to Egypt
- 3- Fayoum University administration paying attention to the academic and social guidance of new students, as the results showed the superiority of Saudi students in the academic and social fields compared to Egypt
- 4- Conducting a study on the relationship between self-concept and self-confidence among early childhood students
- 5- The necessity of paying attention to academic guidance and direction for female students, especially in Egypt
- 6- The necessity of conducting personal interviews for early childhood students before joining the college
- 7- Children's social learning, communication and interaction with others are affected by their self-concept. Because the teacher has a strong influence on the child as a model and role model, the study recommends the importance of seminars and guidance meetings to develop self-confidence and self-esteem among children's teachers

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors extend their appreciation to the Deanship of Scientific Research at Northern Border University, Arar, Saudia Arabia,KSA for funding this research work " through the project number "NBU-FFR-2024-1480-10

References

- [1] Barakat, AMMAR, Gabr, AAA, & Hassan, HHH THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A PROPOSED PROGRAM BASED ON THE STORY STRATEGY TO EDUCATE PRE-SCHOOL MOTHERS ABOUT WAYS TO PROTECT THEIR CHILDREN FROM ELECTRONIC HARASSMENT.
- [2] Dockery, Kathleen A (2017): The effects of sex, and school entrance age on the achievement and self-esteem of ten to eleven year old students. Dissertation Abstract International, Vol. 47, No. 3
- [3] Elizabeth M. Nielsen and Susan MortorfeAldert ; (2018): The effects of special education service on the self-concept and school attitude of learning disabled, gifted students. preper review, Vol.12, No.1
- [4] Elliott, D. & Mekenny , M. (2009). For Inclusion Models that Work. The council For Exceptional children.
- [5] Enam, Shahuria (20 21): Factors Influencing The Development of Self-concept In Pre- Adolescent Boys And Girls, J. Life Earth Sci. Vol. 1, No.2,
- [6] Faas , L. (1 2 20). Learning disabilities: A competency -based approach. Boston : Houghton Mifflin
- [7] Gearheart, B.R., Sileo, T. (2016) Teaching Mildly and Moderately Handicapped Students, Englewood Cliffs, NJ. Prentice-Hall.
- [8] Hallahan, D. P., & Kauffman, J. M. (20 20) Exceptional Children Introduction Special Education. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn and Bacon
- [9] Jensen, Mary - A (2013): Self Concept and its relationship to age family structure and gender, Published as a separate and the journal of psychology
- [10] Johston, C ,. Hessel , D., Blasey , C., Eliez , S., Erba , H., Dyer-Friedman, J., Glaser, B ,. & Reiss, A., (2013), Factors Associated with Parenting Stress in Mothers of Children with Fragile X Syndrome. Developmental and Behavioral Pediatrics, vol 24, No 4,
- [11] Lerner, J. (2013), Learning Disabilities: theories, diagnosis, and teaching strategies (9th Ed). Houghton Mifflin Company, Boston.
- [12] Malone, L.D., & Mastropieri, M.A. (2012). Reading comprehension instruction : Summarization and self-monitoring training for students with learning disabilities. Exceptional Children, 58
- [13] Metwalli , R.M.F., & Barakat, A.M.M.A.R. (2022). The Effectiveness of a Digital Storytelling-based Program on the Development of Geographical Concepts among Kindergarten Children. Int J Edu Sci , 36 (1-3), 1-7.
- [14] Rasmyah , H. (2013). Anxiety and its influence on the political views of Palestinian youngsters, ERIC , Ed, 378440.
- [15] Lo, Ch. (2008), The effect of extra -curricula activities on the self-concept of Taiwanese university students , Dissertation Abstracts International, A, (59)/03, pp. 750.
- [16] Quilter, Shaun, (2015), M, Academic self-concept and the first year college student a snapshot , Journal of the Freshman Year Experience , V 7, n1 pp. 39-52.

- [17] Song, P., & Wang, X. (2020). A bibliometric analysis of worldwide educational artificial intelligence research development in recent twenty years. *Asia Pacific Education Review*, 21(3), 473–486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12564-020-09640-2>
- [18] Yang, Y., Zhuang, Y., & Pan, Y. (2021). Multiple knowledge representation for big data artificial intelligence: framework, applications, and case studies. *Frontiers of Information Technology & Electronic Engineering*, 22(12), 1551–1558. <https://doi.org/10.1631/FITEE.2100463>